

Improving the Teaching of Reading Comprehension Skills through the Use of Resources and Assessment in Colleges of Education in North-West Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined how to improve the teaching of reading comprehension skills through the use of resources and assessment in colleges of education in north-west Nigeria. Four Collages of Education were selected namely; Kano, Kastina, Zamfara and Sokoto were used for the study. 100 subjects were randomly selected to participate in the study. However, only 68 lecturers actually participated in the survey. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze data. The results revealed that while the commonly utilized resources in teaching reading comprehension are text books and journal articles, assessment techniques are homework, impromptu test, and retelling. The study suggested among others, that the use of resources and assessment are significant to the performance of students in reading comprehension and that relevant resources such as language laboratory, video machine, record player, cassette player, radio set, and newspaper articles should be provided and used during teaching and learning of reading comprehension skills. All methods of assessment should be employed appropriately. Government should make available resources for teaching reading and also motivate the lecturers to sustain the use of resources and assessment for an improved performance. This will support in augmenting the quality of their performances and accordingly advance the students' performance as well which in turns has great effects on the performance of students and teacher education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Reading, Comprehension, Resources, Assessment, & Techniques

Introduction

Without reading, ideas and facts stored up in print materials and electronic sources cannot be tapped. Reading therefore, simplifies the academic formation of the student and as such, a child with little interest in reading and in understanding what is read stands at a risk of not performing well in his or her educational career. Smith (2021) opines that reading is a many-sided, very complex activity. It has been variously described as a process, a mode of thinking, a kind of real experience, a type of vicarious experiencing, an aspect of communication, and a tool subject." It means that to complete the process of understanding, reading must be viewed from every angle. In other words, reading involves brain to work, therefore, reading requires full attention to comprehend the content without which little or nothing can be achieved. Reading assists the reader to get new ideas prominent to cognitive development. When the readers transfer what they read to apply with their own ideas, a new viewpoint or idea is generated. Reading is not only a matter of

getting meaning from printed verbal symbols but also the interaction between the graphic symbols and the reader's schema in understanding the text which is comprehension.

Reading comprehension skills are essential for students, professionals, and anyone who wants to read for pleasure or information. Reading comprehension is the capacity to read, internalize, comprehend, and interrelate with the text you are reading. It involves critical thinking and deductive reasoning to make meaning of an entire piece of writing. It's not just about phonological awareness and reading words aloud; it encapsulates language skills such as grammar (syntax), vocabulary, and semantics, to understand the meaning of texts. You make inferences and form an opinion about the read text. Good reading comprehension involves creating images of the words you just read. Readers make connections to previous knowledge as they enjoy the text. They can comfortably answer comprehension questions and summarize parts of the writing or the entire text.

Zhang (2018) defines reading comprehension as "Reading a text with full understanding draws on the reader's background experience, general knowledge, vocabulary, syntactical awareness and word identification skills". Readers with comprehension skills make connections with what they read, they think about the new information in a critical way and come up with new ways to use the formation. Reading allows people to get information from variety of sources, which can help them make better decision. It can also help people understand complex topics and come up with new ideas. It means that, in order to understand text, a reader must be able to identify words rapidly, know the meaning of almost all of the words, and be able to combine sequential units of meaning into a coherent message.

Importance of Reading comprehension skills

Good reading comprehension skills are essential for success in school. Children who develop strong reading comprehension skills are more likely to succeed in school and life. Reading comprehension is the foundation for all other academic skills. It helps children build vocabulary, learn about the world, and understand complex concepts. Adults who improve their reading comprehension skills understand work instructions better. They are more productive at work, communicate effectively, and lead a quality life. If you are struggling with reading comprehension, read on.

Assessment of reading comprehension?

Assessment is a means whereby the teacher obtains information about knowledge gains, behavioural changes and other aspects of the development of learners (Nanda (2020). It involves the deliberate effort of the teacher to measure the effect of the instructional process as well as the overall effect of school learning on the behaviour of students. Assessment covers all aspects of school experience both within and outside the classroom. It covers the cognitive as well as the affective and psychomotor aspects of learning. Assessment is a broad term that includes testing. A test is a special form of assessment. Tests are assessments made under contrived circumstances especially so that they may be administered. In other words, all tests are assessments, but not all assessments are tests. We test at the end of a lesson or unit. We assess progress at the end of a school year through testing, (Saadatnia, 2017).

Reading comprehension tests are measures of identifying specific challenges of students after the teacher has taught the students. Thus, testing should only take place after the teacher has successfully taught the students (Naniwarsih & Andriani, 2018). Assessment helps determine why students have comprehension difficulties, so teachers can develop appropriate instruction to meet

their students' individual needs (Carlson, Seipel, & McMaster, 2014). Prihatin (2020) in contrast, states that the lack of using assessment tool may lead educators to the failure to meet the individual educational needs of students and place them in an inappropriate intervention program, which will negatively impact students' academic achievement (Woolley, 2011, Shabbir, 2019). There are numerous assessment tools and tests available to measure reading than for other academic areas such as formal and informal assessment (Oakhill, Cain & Elbro, 2015). Based on the purpose of this study, the focus of the assessment shall be on the informal reading comprehension assessment and classroom based assessment.

Informal assessment is a type of assessment that is most commonly used by classroom teachers (Ortlieb & Cheek, 2012). Informal assessment is also called Classroom-based assessment. It is known as informal assessment because (1) it is often created by teachers, and (2) its administration does not require following specific procedures to implement the assessment or specific time to finish the test. Mainly, informal assessment is criterion referenced. That is because they assess the students' information on a particular topic or their abilities to perform a pre-determined set of skills as evaluated by some criteria (Ortlieb & Cheek, 2012). Informal classroom-based assessment is a critical component of classrooms' activities. That is because it plays a major role in assisting the teachers to determine the individual strengths, ability, needs, and weakness of each student in the classroom, which helps teachers to better serve a student through the most appropriate instruction based on his/her individual needs. Serafini (2010) refers to several features that make the classroom-based assessment more efficient than standardized tests for assisting teachers to support students' learning. First, classroom-based assessment is frequent. That means that in order to collect data about a students' performance, teachers do not need to stop the student from what they are doing to collect the data. The assessment takes place while students are engaging in the learning process and it ongoing, not only for one day.

Purpose of the Study

This study examined how to improve the teaching of reading comprehension skills through the use of resources and assessment in colleges of education in north-west Nigeria. Specifically, this study is aimed at examining:

- a. resources commonly used for teaching reading comprehension skills in the colleges of education in North-West, Nigeria.
- b. assessment practices for reading comprehension skills in the colleges of education.

Research Questions

In line with the above purpose, this research seeks to find answers to the following research questions.

- a. which resources are commonly used for teaching reading comprehension skills in colleges of education in North- West, Nigeria?
- b. what are the assessment practices for reading comprehension skills in colleges of education in North- West, Nigeria?

Reviewed of related literature

Reading, unlike listening and speaking, is a learned skill. It calls for formal instruction not only in the second language but also in the first language (Adhikari & Poudel, 2020). In academic contexts, students read not only to comprehend a text but also to synthesize, interpret, evaluate, and transfer information from the text to other skills such as reading and writing (Grabe, 2009). Students' ability

to perform multiple and complex tasks on a written text is largely subject to the quality of reading instruction adopted by teachers. Reading is defined as a cognitive process that involves decoding symbols to arrive at meaning. Reading is an active process of constructing meanings of words. Sari (2017) describes reading as information acquired from the text, which could be better done if a picture, diagram or written text or a combination of all is added. She further states that it can also be regarded as a skill to know, see and comprehend the contents of what is read. Sandhu & Bakely (2021) refer to reading as a cognitive procedure that entails decoding symbols to arrive at meaning. They state that reading involves an active means or process of constructing the meaning of words. Joubert (2013) also stresses the importance of comprehension in reading, stating that reading without understanding is of no worth. The reader should be able to form a picture in his or her mind in order to attach meaning to the written concepts.

Andoko (2020) defines reading as one of the important activities to obtain knowledge or information. In other words, reading is one of the gateways of knowledge. It is an active and fluent process involving the readers and the reading materials building meaning. It is also noticed as an active task where readers are making selection from a range of words, derive from the text and the situational context that are constructing a model of meaning that reflects, more or less the same, the meaning designated by the writer.” From the statement, we can understand that reading is an activity to get meaning and also how is used to recognize and understand the printed of words or symbols so that the reader can understand the meaning of passage and also catch the meaning of text. Reading is the reservoir in which ideas and facts stored up in printed materials and electronic sources cannot be tapped. In view of this, reading is regarded indispensable in education as it promotes cognitive growth (Beard, 2021).

Another crucial component to understanding reading comprehension is its assessment or measurement. There exist many different methods of testing students' reading comprehension. Assessment is a means whereby the teacher obtains information about knowledge gains, behavioral changes and other aspects of the development of learners (Nanda (2020). It involves the deliberate effort of the teacher to measure the effect of the instructional process as well as the overall effect of school learning on the behavior of students. Assessment covers all aspects of school experience both within and outside the classroom. It covers the cognitive as well as the affective and psychomotor aspects of learning. Assessment is a broad term that includes testing. A test is a special form of assessment. Tests are assessments made under contrived circumstances especially so that they may be administered. In other words, all tests are assessments, but not all assessments are tests. We test at the end of a lesson or unit. We assess progress at the end of a school year through testing, (Saadatnia,2017).

Reading comprehension tests are measures of identifying specific challenges of students after the teacher has taught the students. Thus, testing should only take place after the teacher has successfully taught the students (Naniwarsih & Andriani,2018). Comprehension skills such as skills of predicting, self-questioning, and evaluating, summarizing, clarifying and vocabulary development (Shemshadsara, 2019). But there is a difference between teaching and testing comprehension. When a teacher of reading comprehension reads a passage or asks students to read a passage and attempt the questions that follow, he/she has not taught but tested. When a teacher teaches learners through modelling and calls into play the learners' knowledge, such a teacher is engaged in teaching and when the students are evaluated, the complementary teaching and testing paradigms reveal the appropriate mode of teaching.

Instructional materials are sometimes referred to as resources, media, teaching aid etc. that can be used to facilitate effective teaching and learning. The instructional materials in the words of Ajayi (2018) are those things which can be an object of study or stimulus to the pupils or to aid the teacher. This he said can include print form, audio visual, mass communication items specimen and items in the locality. It could be human, material or environmental. According to Adeniyi (2012), instructional materials are things or devices within which there are incorporated in educational values or content used to facilitate teaching and learning and achievement of educational goals and objectives.

Lawal (2019) viewed “materials” as a concept that is subsumed under “resources”. He explained that “resources” is of wider coverage than “materials”, meaning that material is an aspect of resources. He explained further that resources could either be human or non-human. The human resources are divided into two types, school based and non-school based for community resources. Further still, the school based resources are divided into English and non- English resources; the English human resources are the teachers of English language and literature in English while the non- English human resources are the teachers of mathematics, economics, physics, commerce etc. the non-school based human resources are professionals and experts who are usually invited to deliver lecture on certain topics in which they are experts. Conversely, the non-human resources are divided into two; plant and materials. Just as in the case of human resources, plant resources are sub-divided into school and non-school based ones. The school based non-human resources include programmed instructor, classrooms, language laboratory and educational television etc. while non-school based plant resources are resources like media house, hospital, Zoo, stadium etc. Material non- human resources could be audio, visual, audio-visual and multi-sensory materials.

Methods and Materials

Descriptive research approach via cross sectional survey was employed during the course of this study. This has to do with direct contact with the sampled population that has the characteristics which are relevant to what the study intends to investigate. This is the type that deals with generally collecting data from a defined population to describe the present condition using the variables under study. The population of the study was the totality of lecturers of English department/use of English in Colleges of Education in North-Central, Nigeria. This was because the lecturers at Colleges of Education within this area have common characteristics since they operate under a uniform educational system and practices, educational standard, cultural patterns and other historical antecedents.

The sample of this research therefore consisted of lecturers from four (4) selected Colleges of Education across the North-West, Nigeria namely: Federal College of Education, Kano; Federal College of Education Katsina; Federal College of Education (Technical) Gusau; and Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto states, respectively. The sampled lecturers of English /Use of English was 100 and were randomly selected across the colleges. Simple random sampling technique was used. Researcher-designed questionnaire which had content and face validated was designed and administered to lecturers to elicit information. The questionnaire was divided into sections A and B. Section B was further divided into sub-sections I & II. Section A contain the personal data of lecturers. It was designed to get the demographic information of lecturers that participated in the survey. Sub-section I & II of section B focused on resources and assessment techniques employed in teaching reading comprehension respectively. The items were designed using the five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree representing “1” to strongly agree

represented by five “5”. Since the upper limit of 2.50 is 3.00, any items whose mean score is 2.50 or greater was regarded as adequate thus, accepted. While the items whose mean score is less than 2.50 was considered inadequate thus, rejected.

The researchers personally administered the instruments with the help of a research assistant after due permission from authorities of the concerned Colleges of Education. The researcher informed the respondents on the purpose of the questionnaire. As for demographic information of participants, the percentage approach to data analysis was adopted. Whereas mean and standard deviation tools of descriptive statistics were employed to analyze the resources, techniques, and assessment procedures adopted by English Language lecturers for teaching reading comprehension.

RESULTS

Demographic information of participants

Table 1 represents analysis of data on demographic information of participants. The demographic data include gender of respondents, educational background, length of time working in the current institution, and lastly, the overall work experience of participants.

Table I: *Demographic Information of Respondents*

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	48	70.6
Female	20	29.4
Total	68	100
Educational qualification		
Bachelor's Degree	4	5.9
PGDE	21	30.9
Master's Degree	31	45.6
PhD	12	17.6
Total	68	100
Length of time teaching in the current institution		
A month – 11 months	3	4.4
1 – 5 years	12	17.6
6 – 10 years	28	41.2
11 years and above	25	36.8
Total	68	100
Years of experience		
Less than a year -5 years	3	4.4
6-10 years	10	14.7
11-15 years	12	17.6
Over 15 years	43	63.3
Total	68	100

Analysis of data in Table I indicates that 48 male representing 70.6 % and 20 female representing 29.4 % participated in this survey. Pertaining to educational background of respondents, 45.6% of participants hold a master’s degree. While 30.9% of respondents had obtained postgraduate diploma in education (PGDE), 17.6% are PhD holders. On the part of bachelor’s degree, only 5.9% of respondents possess first degree as a highest educational qualification.

The study equally sought for insights about the length of time respondents had put up with their current employer. Table I demonstrates that 41.2% of participants had spent between six and ten years working in the current institution. Further, the analysis shows that 36.8% of participants had spent 11 years or more with their current employer. While 17.6% of respondents had spent between one and five years teaching in their current institution, only 4.4% had less than a year teaching in current institution.

It is interesting to note that 63.3% of participants had over 15 years of teaching experience. While 17.6% of respondents had between 11 and 15 years of teaching experience, 14.7% had between six and ten years. However, the proportion of respondents (4.4%) with least teaching experience was those that had less than a year in the profession.

Instructional resources for teaching reading comprehension skills

Table II contains analysis of statements on resources used in teaching reading comprehension.

Table II *Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses on Instructional Resources for Reading Comprehension*

S/n	Item	Mean	SD	Decision
1	There is a language laboratory in my department	2.42	0.91	Disagree
2	I utilize video machine in teaching reading comprehension	2.40	0.97	Disagree
3	I use record player in reading comprehension class	2.38	0.99	Disagree
4	I utilize cassette player in teaching reading comprehension	1.70	0.91	Disagree
5	In teaching reading comprehension, I use text books	2.59	1.00	Agree
6	I use radio set in teaching reading comprehension skills	1.60	0.95	Disagree
7	During reading comprehension class, I utilize journal articles	3.01	0.85	Agree
8	I utilize newspaper articles in teaching reading comprehension	2.02	1.03	Disagree
Overall Mean and Standard Deviation		2.27	1.10	Disagree

From Table II, results of the analysis show that only two items (i.e., items 5 & 7) had mean score greater than 2.50. On the other the hand, the remaining items (i.e., items 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, & 8) had mean score less than 2.50. The overall mean score (2.27) fell short of the threshold set in this study. This indicates that the facility and instructional resources specified in the NCCE minimum standard for effective teaching of reading comprehension skills are either not in place or not put into use.

Table III: *Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses on Assessment Techniques Used in Reading Comprehension*

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I give class exercise in each reading comprehension lesson	2.41	0.76	Disagree
2	I give homework on reading comprehension at the end of each lesson	3.42	0.72	Agree
3	I split students into groups for reading comprehension purposes	2.36	0.77	Disagree
4	I administer impromptu test on reading comprehension at any time	3.27	0.82	Agree
5	I adopt a retelling approach in assessing students' reading comprehension skills	3.20	0.81	Agree
Overall mean and standard deviation		2.93	0.80	Agree

Table III displays results of the analysis of mean and standard deviation of statements concerning assessment techniques used in building reading comprehension skills in learners. Out of five items, three items (i.e., 2, 4, & 5) were accepted because each had mean score greater than 2.50. Whereas items 1, & 3 had mean scores less than 2.50. This implies that participants rarely observe class exercises during reading comprehension lessons. However, the overall mean score for the five items was 2.93 which exceeds the threshold of 2.50.

Discussion and Conclusion

The first research question bothers on identifying commonly used resources for teaching reading comprehension skills in colleges of education in North-West, Nigeria. The analysis of data revealed that only text books and journal articles are commonly utilized for teaching reading comprehension skills in colleges of education in North-West, Nigeria. Other resources such as language laboratory, video machine, record player, cassette player, radio set, and newspaper articles are not commonly utilized for teaching reading comprehension skills in the settings of this study. This finding indicates non-compliance with the provision of NCCE minimum standard to effectively teach reading comprehension skills in colleges of education in Nigeria. However, it is imperative to mention that extant literature point out that the use of learning resources in general, enhance students' reading comprehension skills (Ajayi, 2018; Andoko, 2020; Lawal, 2019; Shemshadsara, 2019; Zhang, 2018). Therefore, to have effective teaching of reading comprehension in place, utilization of teaching resources is not only important but necessary.

The second research question pertains to assessment practices for reading comprehension skills in colleges of education in North-West, Nigeria. Analysis of the results demonstrates that assessment techniques such as homework, impromptu test, and retelling were utilized by lecturers in the study area. These assessment practices expose students' strengths and weaknesses in reading which further provides robust insights for lecturers to make suitable adjustment. However, the lecturers are not in the habit of assessing the reading comprehension skills of learners via class exercises and group work. In the researchers' opinion, if class exercises and group work assessment techniques were utilized, learners would have gained better understanding or knowledge of reading comprehension skills. From the discussion of findings, one can conclude that the use of resources

in teaching reading comprehension is limited to a larger extent within the settings of this study. However, variety of assessment techniques are utilized by the lecturers. It may be appropriate to observe that students may not be better than what they have not been exposed to. In other words, assessing the reading comprehension skills of students without exposing them to the nitty gritty of reading comprehension may not make students skillful in reading comprehension. Thus, using resources and assessment will enable students connect to the content and comprehend the material.

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